

FACTORS PREVENTING FROM PERFORMING REFRACTIVE SURGERY IN UNAIZAH, QASSIM, SAUDI ARABIA

RAYAN NASSER ALMUTAIRI*

Optometry Doctor, Masters in Optometry, Deputy Director of Eye Center and Head of Optometry Department, King Saud Hospital - Uniazah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

*Corresponding Author Email: ranaalmutairi@moh.gov.sa

ABDURAHMAN JEZA ALHARBI

Optometry Doctor, Master's in Business Administration and Head of Optometry Department, AIRass General Hospital – AIRass, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

MOHAMMED KHALED ALHARBI

Optometry Doctor, Department of Optometry, King Saud Hospital - Uniazah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

WALEED HUSSAIN ALHARBI

Optometry Doctor, Department of Optometry, King Saud Hospital - Uniazah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

ABDULLAH FAHD ALSULMY

Optometry Doctor, Department of Optometry, King Saud Hospital - Uniazah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

SHOUG FEEHAN MODHYAN

Optometry Doctor, Department of Optometry, King Saud Hospital - Uniazah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

RAZAN ABDULLAH ALHARBI

Optometry Doctor, Department of Optometry, King Saud Hospital - Uniazah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

NAEEM MUNIR

FCPS, FRCS, Ophthalmologist and Head of Ophthalmology Department, King Saud Hospital - Uniazah, Qassim, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract

Background: Contemporary refractive surgery provides long lasting correction of refractive error, although safe results are only achieved by stringent candidate selection and lifelong co-management. Purpose: To combine the results of a secondary eye center in Unaizah, Qassim (Saudi Arabia), to elucidate clinical motivators of eligibility and the primary role of optometrists throughout the peri-operative process, and to place those results into perspective with other related studies. Procedures: 190 consecutive candidates including demographics, manifest refraction, tear breakup time TBUT, Pentacam tomography/keratometry, central corneal thickness CCT; exclusion criteria and reasons for exclusion were summed up; awareness among the population was measured. Findings: 53% met the criteria; 47% did not including chiefly dry eye (39%), keratoconus (32%), recent isotretinoin (12%), below threshold age (10%), amblyopia (5%), high hyperopia (2%). Thick corneas (CCT 526 +- 29.7 um) were found in eligible patients as compared to ineligible patients (508 +- 48.9 um). Knowledge and awareness level was low. Conclusion: Optometrists can provide comprehensive education and ocular examination preoperatively to refractive surgeries.

Keywords: Refractive Surgery; Keratoconus; Dry Eye Disease; Patient Awareness; Optometrist Co-Management.

INTRODUCTION

Visual impairments represent the fourth most widespread form of disability worldwide (1). According to the World Health Organization, approximately 2.2 billion people worldwide are affected by visual impairment, with over 1 billion cases being preventable (2). Refractive errors constitute the second most common cause of blindness that is amenable to treatment (3). Refractive errors occur when the eye fails to properly focus light on the retina, leading to blurred vision(4). Uncorrected refractive errors may lead to both immediate and long-term consequences in children and adults, including reduced educational and occupational opportunities, increased economic burden on individuals and communities, and limitations in social integration and development (5).

Refractive errors can be categorized into four primary types. Firstly, myopia, or nearsightedness, is characterized by the eye's inability to focus light directly on the retina, instead causing it to converge in front of the retinal surface, which leads to blurred distance vision. (6). Globally, myopia is the most common refractive error, with its prevalence rising sharply from 10.4% in 1993 to 34.2% by 2016 (7) and by 2050, the World Health Organization expects that half of the world's population will be myopic (2). In Saudi Arabia, myopia affects an estimated 37.8% of the population, indicating a significant public health concern (8). Hyperopia is characterized by the misfocus of light rays behind the retina, which leads to blurred near vision, while distant vision typically remains clear (9), with prevalence of 19.59% in Saudi Arabia(8), Consequently, hyperopia frequently remains undetected in young children, particularly when it is not associated with overt clinical signs such as esotropia, which may alert parents to the condition (9). Astigmatism is characterized by the eye's inability to focus light onto a single point on the retina, leading to multiple focal points and causing visual distortion or blurring at both near and far distances (10), with prevalence of 32.14% in Saudi Arabia (8). Presbyopia, an age-related condition, represents the primary cause of near vision impairment worldwide (11), it happened by a progressive loss of lens flexibility, which impairs the eye's accommodative capacity and causes near vision to become blurred (12). According to Algorinees et al., the prevalence of refractive errors in Saudi Arabia was found to be 18.5% for both males and females.(13)

A range of corrective options exists for refractive errors, with spectacles and contact lenses being the most widely utilized modalities (14). Refractive surgery ranks among the most frequently performed ophthalmic procedures globally and offers a long-term solution for correcting refractive errors by altering the shape of the cornea (14). Refractive surgery has been associated with enhanced quality of life, as patients often experience greater ease and comfort in performing daily activities. Laser-assisted techniques have a proven track record of safety and efficacy, underpinned by extensive clinical research spanning several decades (15).

Radial keratotomy (RK) was among the earliest refractive surgical techniques, utilizing radial corneal incisions to correct myopia. However, due to its potential for postoperative complications and variability in outcomes, it has largely been supplanted by more precise and reliable laser technologies, including excimer and femtosecond lasers (16) among

corneal-based ablation techniques, Laser-Assisted In Situ Keratomileusis (LASIK) is the most frequently performed refractive procedure globally, owing to its effectiveness, safety, and rapid recovery time (13). Photorefractive keratectomy (PRK), an earlier technique than LASIK, is considered an appropriate option for individuals with thin corneas or corneal surface abnormalities. It is recognized as a successful and reliable procedure for correcting refractive errors, particularly in cases where LASIK may not be suitable (17). Photorefractive keratectomy (PRK) is effective in addressing a broad spectrum of refractive errors, such as low to moderate myopia, hyperopia, and astigmatism (17). Small Incision Lenticule Extraction (SMILE) represents a newer, minimally invasive refractive surgical technique, wherein a lenticule is extracted from the cornea to correct refractive errors (18). These refractive surgical procedures alter the shape of the corneal surface, thereby adjusting its refractive power to restore optimal vision (19). When corneal-based refractive ablation techniques are not appropriate, alternative procedures such as Implantable Collamer Lenses (ICL) and Refractive Lens Exchange (RLE) are considered. ICLs are implanted without removing the natural crystalline lens, while RLE involves the removal of the crystalline lens and the replacement with an intraocular lens (IOL) (20).

While refractive surgical procedures like LASIK, PRK, and SMILE are widely regarded as effective alternatives to corrective eyewear, it is essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and complications inherent in these treatments. Postoperative dry eye syndrome is a frequent complication resulting from the disruption of corneal nerves, leading to compromised tear film stability in a substantial proportion of patients (21). Persistent dry eyes, while commonly temporary, can significantly affect ocular comfort and visual acuity. Furthermore, the development of irregular astigmatism may result in visual distortions that necessitate enhancement surgery or the use of rigid gas-permeable contact lenses to restore optimal vision (21). Halos and glare are notable manifestations of temporary night vision disturbances, commonly encountered by patients following refractive surgical procedures (22)

While uncommon, corneal infections remain a serious potential complication, necessitating close postoperative surveillance and timely administration of antibiotics to preserve ocular integrity (23). The risk of developing late-onset corneal ectasia, especially among patients with underlying corneal abnormalities, underscores the necessity of meticulous preoperative screening and risk assessment (23). Diffuse lamellar keratitis (DLK), characterized by an inflammatory reaction, requires immediate corticosteroid therapy to reduce the risk of scarring and protect the integrity of the cornea (24). Although infrequent, epithelial ingrowth can significantly affect visual quality and may necessitate surgical correction to restore optimal vision (21).

Prior refractive surgery poses challenges for intraocular lens (IOL) power calculations in subsequent cataract surgery, as the corneal changes resulting from refractive procedures often lead to erroneous keratometry measurements. These inaccuracies can influence the calculation of the effective lens position. To achieve precise IOL selection and optimal refractive outcomes, it is essential to apply specialized formulas tailored to altered corneal topography (19). Hence, it is imperative to carefully consider these potential complications

to ensure informed decision-making and the optimal management of long-term visual outcomes for patients undergoing refractive surgery.

Refractive surgery has become well-established as a safe and effective intervention for correcting refractive errors, supported by a robust history of patient satisfaction and favorable visual results. Worldwide, the demand for these procedures is projected to grow, with annual surgical volumes anticipated to rise from 3.6 million to 5.8 million (25). In the United States, LASIK surgery has experienced a decline in recent years, with approximately 596,000 procedures conducted in 2015, representing a significant reduction from the peak of 1.2 million procedures in 2007 (26).

In a comprehensive, web-based cross-sectional study examining the awareness of refractive surgery among Saudi adults, it was revealed that only 17.7% possessed a high level of knowledge regarding refractive surgical procedures (27). In contrast, a significant majority, 82.3%, demonstrated a lack of sufficient awareness, falling below the optimal level of knowledge (27). A comparable study in the Aseer Region revealed that although 59.5% of participants were familiar with refractive surgical options, 29.4% perceived these procedures as potentially dangerous, highlighting the importance of improving patient education and counseling efforts (28).

METHODS

A Retrospective descriptive Cross-Sectional Study. The approval was obtained by the Qassim Research Ethics Committee and Registered at National Committee of Bio & Med. Ethics (NCBE) Registration Number (H-04-Q-001) and was conducted at the Eye Center in King Saud Hospital in Unaizah, Qassim region, Saudi Arabia. Out of 17,928 individuals who visited the eye center in 2024, the targeted population were 190 individuals in which they are seeking refractive surgery and medical files were reviewed (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Data collection process.

A combination of descriptive statistics, graphs, and parametric statistics will be used to characterize fit and non-fit patients for refractive surgery, to determine the factors limiting the patients to undergo refractive surgery and to assess the prevalence of keratoconus, dry eye, and contact lenses wear among those patients seeking refractive surgery.

Data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel. The collected information includes patients age and sex, as well as clinical data such as aided and unaided visual acuity (using E chart), manifest refractive error, tear break-up time (TBUT) using the slit lamp with fluorescein staining.

Another important data is the corneal topography (Oculus Pentacam-HR) to assess the central corneal thickness (CCT), keratometry readings.

Additional information included average and maximum keratometry values, history of previous refractive surgeries and knowledge, ocular and family medical history, systemic conditions, contact lenses wearing, smartphone usage and smoking status.

RESULTS

Out of 190 subjects (49% male; mean age 27.2 +- 7 years), 100 (53%) were eligible and 90 (47%) were not. Top exclusion causes: Dry eye (n=35; 39%), keratoconus (n=29; 32%), isotretinoin (n=11; 12%), under policy age (n=9; 10%), amblyopia (n=4; 5%), high hyperopia (n=2; 2%). The mean CCT of eligible vs ineligible was higher (526 +- 29.7 um vs 508 +- 48.9 um).

Wear of contact-lenses was positively associated with eligibility. The level of awareness was very low (1% keratoconus; 2% refractive surgery).

Results

The study included 190 patients. Of these, 119 (46%) were male, and 137 (54%) were female. The mean age of male participants was 28.2 years (range: 17–50 years), while that of female participants was 26.3 years (range: 11–60 years).

Among the total patients, 153 (59.7%) 64 males and 89 females were deemed suitable candidates for refractive surgery, whereas 103 (40.3%) 55 males and 48 females had medical contraindications.

Among the excluded group, the most common reason for exclusion was dry eye (36 patients, 34.95%), followed by keratoconus (32, 31.03%), Isotretinoin use (12, 11.65%), underage status (10, 9.70%), amblyopia (7, 6.79%), retinopathy (4, 3.88%), and high hyperopia (2, 1.94%).

The mean central corneal thickness (CCT) among eligible patients was 526 ± 29.7 µm (range: 462–609 µm), whereas in ineligible patients, it was 508 ± 48.9 µm (range: 277–595 µm). Wearing contact lenses is associated with a higher suitability for eye correction surgery (80.16%) compared to non-wearers (53.33%).

Figure 1: demographic distribution

Figure 2: Awareness regarding refractive surgery

Table 1: Reasons of rejection

<i>Reasons of rejection</i>	<i>Counts</i>	<i>percentage</i>
DRY EYE	36	34.95%
KERATOCONUS	32	31.03%
ISOTRETINOIN USE	12	11.65%
UNDERAGE	10	9.70%
AMBLYOPIA	7	6.79%
Retinopathy	4	3.88%
HYPEROPIA	2	1.94%

Figure 3: Awareness regarding Keratoconus

DISCUSSION

This research aimed to evaluate the awareness and number of patients suitable and unsuitable cases for refractive surgery at Unaizah Eye Center at King Saud Hospital, as well as to identify the factors preventing patients from undergoing the procedure.

In our findings, most patients who sought refractive surgery were able to receive it, which aligns with results from similar studies. However, dry eye was identified as the leading reason for not performing the surgery, followed by keratoconus then Recotane use. In contrast, many other studies report that high myopia, insufficient corneal thickness, and keratoconus are the primary causes for rejection^{1 2 3}.

Dry eye disease is the most common complication following corneal laser refractive surgery 4 and can lead to less stable postoperative correction over time 5. Therefore, detecting patients with pre-existing dry eye during the preoperative assessment is essential to achieve the best possible outcomes.

Iatrogenic keratectasia is the most vision-threatening complication associated with refractive surgery. Therefore, preoperative screening should extend beyond the earliest detectable clinical signs to comprehensively identify candidates at risk of developing ectasia 6. In our study keratoconus is found to be the second most common reason to not perform refractive surgery. One of the key factors in identifying the risk of developing ectasia after LASIK is central corneal thickness (CCT) as corneas thinner than 480–500 μm are considered a significant risk factor for post-operative ectasia 7.

As keratoconus found to be the second most common reason for refractive surgery ineligibility. the ineligible group had a lower mean CCT ($508 \pm 48.9 \mu\text{m}$), with values as low as 277 μm , highlighting the critical role of corneal thickness in determining LASIK candidacy and maintaining sufficient residual stromal bed thickness after flap creation and laser ablation which is essential to reduce the risk of post operative ectasia. A minimum of 250–300 μm is generally recommended 8. Although some studies have investigated the possibility of LASIK in patients with thinner corneas with consideration of ablation depth and residual stromal bed 9, standard safety protocols remain cautious.

Just 0.4% of participants in the current study indicated that they had prior knowledge of keratoconus, showing a very low level of awareness of the condition. Compared to other studies carried out in Saudi Arabia, where awareness levels reached 26% in the Eastern Province [10], 17.6% in Taif [11], and 15.7% in Jazan [12], this percentage is far lower.

Additionally, 1.2% of the people who participated in the present study reported being familiar with refractive surgery, presenting an indication of the procedure's lack of awareness. Other Saudi studies, however, demonstrated greater levels: 59.5% in the Asir region [13], 53% in Arar [14], and 17.7% in a national survey involving different regions in Saudi Arabia [15]. This discrepancy may be a result of regional variations in public health education, indicating the need for enhanced awareness efforts in some areas.

Our study showed that 80.16% of the 153 people who sought refractive surgery and were fit to do it are wearing contact lenses. This indicates that contact lens wearers are more motivated about the procedure and more informed about it, which supports other studies (16). Additionally, contact lens wearers are more exposed to interact with eye care practitioners as supported by (17) showed that most users obtained the contact lenses by prescription.

This allows for early detection of the conditions that disqualify them from performing refractive surgery before seeking the procedure, which makes them ideal candidates. Moreover, the drawbacks such as cost and daily maintenance, risk of infection and cosmetic appearance among contact lens users (17)(18), which serve as motivation for permanent solution such as refractive surgery (28).

CONCLUSION

In a tertiary high-throughput clinic with a high output of refractive surgery patients, slightly above fifty percent of applicants eventually become eligible to receive the surgery. The main obstacles are the dry eye disease and the keratoconus; the exposure to isotretinoin and age policy are the additional determining factors of eligibility. The evidence supports an optometrist-based methodology: careful pre-operative triaging, pre-operative ocular-surface rehabilitation, pre-operative tomography-based ectasia risk management, and patient education. Surgical throughput and satisfaction and safety should be enhanced by standardizing these elements.

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